

Spatial Arithmetic – Some Explanations

Spatial Arithmetic explain What “time” is. The unit of spatial value S
Time is essentially space. We can completely convert time to space, using the same unit "S".

The true nature of reality, spacetime, is not a background field (there is no curvature of spacetime). Space is time and vice versa. This is the transformation of the unit of spatial value S as energy moves. The system of energy is like a money bag that always generates S; if the energy moves, it uses this money to exchange for space, and the remaining money is time with an equivalent conversion: $1 S = 1 s^2$ (s is second) = $1 c^2 \text{ km}^2$ (c^2 approximately 300.000^2).

t^2 is the total spatial value of a system of energy, meaning when it is in the stationary frame.

$(t')^2$ is the remaining untransformed spatial value of the system when energy move creating SV (the transformed spatial value) with $SV = t^2 - (t')^2 = q^2 / c^2$ (q is the distance covered by the kinetic energy).

Spatial arithmetic explains mass, energy, and particles – Law of conservation of spatial value

E is energy, the kinetic energy that creates spatial value, equivalent to 1 S or a spatial fraction $c^2 \text{ km}^2$. Thus, we can represent (map) $E = tc^2$. Here, it doesn't mean E increases over time, but rather represents the creation of spatial value.

Mass is essentially the spatial value of the energy system that has not yet been transformed into space.

Law of Conservation of Spatial Value: $t^2 = SV + (t')^2$

Spatial arithmetic explains the intrinsic frequency of particles

I proved that mass (what we call matter) is essentially time (t'), an untransformed spatial value. The same applies to the formula: $f/f_0 = t'/t$.

Spatial arithmetic states the Deterministic Principle of Reality

Spatial arithmetic states the Deterministic Principle of Reality: $1 = SV/t^2 + (f/f_0)^2$

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.